

Spawning S_4 from Kronecker products

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The symmetric group S_4 has the following 24 permutation-matrix representation, using ordering as in [1]:

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 \pi_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_7 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_8 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_9 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{10} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{11} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{13} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{14} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{15} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{16} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{17} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{18} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{19} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{20} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{21} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{22} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{array}$$

These matrices are:

1. Orthogonal: $\pi_K^{-1} = \pi_K'$ for all K
2. Hadamard idempotent: $\pi_K \otimes \pi_K = \pi_K$ for all K
3. Involutional for $K = 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 14, 16, 21,$ and 23 : $\pi_K^2 = \pi_0$
4. Symmetric for these same indices : $\pi_K' = \pi_K$
5. Skew-involutional for $k = 10$ and 13 : $\pi_{10}^2 = \pi_{13}^2 = \pi_{23}$
6. Commutative for: $(\pi_2, \pi_{21}), (\pi_2, \pi_{23}), (\pi_{21}, \pi_{23}), (\pi_7, \pi_{16}), (\pi_7, \pi_{23}), (\pi_{16}, \pi_{23})$

It is remarkable that the skew-diagonal π_{23} not only commutes individually with the four permutations $\pi_2, \pi_7, \pi_{16},$ and $\pi_{21},$ but also equals the products $\pi_2 * \pi_{21}$ and $\pi_7 * \pi_{16}.$

The table below catalogs basic features of these matrices, including trace, determinant, commutators, cyclicity, and spectrum; a detailed Cayley analysis is available in [1].

	trace	det	comm	$\wedge^2$	$\wedge^3$	$\wedge^4$	eig
π_0	4	1		π_0			1,1,1,1
π_1	2	-1		π_0			-1,1,1,1
π_2	2	-1	π_{21}, π_{23}	π_0			-1,1,1,1
π_3	1	1		π_4	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_4	1	1		π_3	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_5	2	-1		π_0			-1,1,1,1
π_6	2	-1		π_0			-1,-1,1,1
π_7	0	1	π_{16}, π_{23}	π_0			-1,-1,1,1
π_8	1	1		π_{12}	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_9	0	-1		π_{16}	π_{18}	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{10}	0	-1		π_{23}	π_{13}	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{11}	1	1		π_{19}	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_{12}	1	1		π_8	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_{13}	0	-1		π_{23}	π_{10}	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{14}	2	-1		π_0			-1,1,1,1
π_{15}	1	1		π_{20}	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_{16}	0	1	π_7, π_{23}	π_0			-1,-1,1,1
π_{17}	0	-1		π_7	π_{22}	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{18}	0	-1		π_{16}	π_9	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{19}	1	1		π_{11}	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_{20}	1	1		π_{15}	π_0		$-1/2(1-\sqrt{3}i), -1/2(1+\sqrt{3}i), 1, 1$
π_{21}	2	-1	π_2, π_{23}	π_0			-1,1,1,1
π_{22}	0	-1		π_7	π_{17}	π_0	-1,i,-i,1
π_{23}	0	1	$\pi_2, \pi_7, \pi_{16}, \pi_{21}$	π_0			-1,-1,1,1

And now, on to spawning the 64 elements of S_4 .

The smallest symmetry group is S_2 , whose matrices are:

$$s_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad s_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Kronecker products evolve $2^2 = 4$ 'parents' (also the Core) of S_4 ; in OCTAVE shorthand:

$$\mathbf{kron}(s_0, s_1) = \pi_7, \quad \mathbf{kron}(s_1, s_0) = \pi_{16}, \quad \mathbf{kron}(s_0, s_0) = \pi_0, \quad \mathbf{kron}(s_1, s_1) = \pi_{23}$$

These commute and sum to a matrix of all 1's.

Now, parental pairing here yields $nchoosek(4,2) = 6$ couples; a 'fill-the-gaps' process applied to each matrix sum would then spawn 'twins', so twelve in all. To see one example

$$\pi_{16} + \pi_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \pi_1 \text{ \& } \pi_6$$

The sum $\pi_{16} + \pi_{23}$ 'spawns' π_1 (in red) and π_6 (in blue); the full list follows.

$$\pi_0 + \pi_7 \rightarrow \pi_{17} \text{ \& } \pi_{22} \quad \pi_0 + \pi_{16} \rightarrow \pi_9 \text{ \& } \pi_{18} \quad \pi_0 + \pi_{23} \rightarrow \pi_{10} \text{ \& } \pi_{13}$$

$$\pi_7 + \pi_{16} \rightarrow \pi_2 \text{ \& } \pi_{21} \quad \pi_7 + \pi_{23} \rightarrow \pi_5 \text{ \& } \pi_{14} \quad \pi_{16} + \pi_{23} \rightarrow \pi_1 \text{ \& } \pi_6$$

The sixteen generated matrices – parents (yellow highlight) and offspring – are:

$$\pi_0, \pi_1, \pi_2, \pi_5, \pi_6, \pi_7, \pi_9, \pi_{10}, \pi_{13}, \pi_{14}, \pi_{16}, \pi_{17}, \pi_{18}, \pi_{21}, \pi_{22}, \text{ and } \pi_{23}.$$

Eight elements remain to complete S_4 :

$$\pi_3, \pi_4, \pi_8, \pi_{11}, \pi_{12}, \pi_{15}, \pi_{19}, \text{ and } \pi_{20}$$

The twelve offspring now spawn their own twins (plus bonus clones!) to fill out S_4 ; replicating their parental method (after some labor) the results are:

$$\pi_1 + \pi_{17} \rightarrow \pi_8 \text{ \& } \pi_{19} \quad \pi_2 + \pi_{10} \rightarrow \pi_{15} \text{ \& } \pi_{19} \quad \pi_5 + \pi_9 \rightarrow \pi_{12} \text{ \& } \pi_{20}$$

$$\pi_6 + \pi_{22} \rightarrow \pi_4 \text{ \& } \pi_{15} \quad \pi_{13} + \pi_{21} \rightarrow \pi_4 \text{ \& } \pi_8 \quad \pi_{14} + \pi_{18} \rightarrow \pi_3 \text{ \& } \pi_{11}$$

Thus Kronecker build-up, then 'add and fill' spawned S_4 in just two generations.

A more challenging effort is to generate the 720 elements of S_6 by Kronecker evolution from S_2 and S_3 , then use the 'add-and-fill' process. The six elements of S_3 are

$$p_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

These six parents, plus the two from S_2 , generate 24 Kronecker-evolved options:

$$\text{kron}(s_0, p_j) \equiv s_0 p_j, \text{ kron}(s_1, p_j) \equiv s_1 p_j, \text{ kron}(p_j, s_0) \equiv p_j s_0, \text{ kron}(p_j, s_1) \equiv p_j s_1; j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$$

However, only 22 are unique;

$$\text{kron}(s_0, p_1) = \text{kron}(p_1, s_0) = I_6, \text{ the } 6 \times 6 \text{ identity matrix, and}$$

$$\text{kron}(s_1, p_2) = \text{kron}(p_2, s_1) = C_6, \text{ the } 6 \times 6 \text{ counter (or skew) identity matrix}$$

All evolved matrices are orthogonal, hence belong in S_6 .

Three parenting options are available here: $nchoosek(24,2) = 231$ couplings, $nchoosek(14,3) = 1,540$ threesomes, and $nchoosek(14,4) = 7,315$ foursomes; clearly an overabundance of parents for S_6 . However, the (0,1) nature of parental sums whittled down first-generation offspring.

By direct computation in OCTAVE, only 135 couplings were (0,1) matrices, for a total of $135 \times 4 = 540$ siblings, though perhaps not unique; even so, parents + offspring = 562, a healthy first generation of S_6 . The chart of cumulative couplings does show diminishing options.

A minimal effort to find threesomes with a (0,1) matrix sum yielded 52 sets, hence $52 \times 3 = 156$ offspring; and 12 foursome sets yielded 24 offspring. The grand total then, including the twosomes results above plus threesomes and foursomes, yielded 742 elements, overflowing S_6 . However, as was the case for S_4 , duplication of generated elements most likely occurred.

Three exemplars are provided below, from twosome, threesome, and foursome parenting; offspring are highlighted individually, including a duplicate skew-diagonal in green.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{kron}(s_0, p_2) + \text{kron}(s_0, p_3) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \text{kron}(s_0, p_2) + \text{kron}(s_0, p_3) + \text{kron}(s_0, p_4) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \text{kron}(s_0, p_2) + \text{kron}(p_2, s_0) + \text{kron}(p_3, s_1) + \text{kron}(p_4, s_1) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

Kronecker evolution should eventually spawn out even larger symmetric matrix groups, once these heuristics become algorithms.

To return now to S_4 , its parents are at the vertices of the tetrahedron below; the first generation is on the edges, using index numerals only to reduce clutter. Below that is the full family tree, numerals only; parent pairings are colored in yellow, first generation in blue, and second in green. The tree, if somewhat overcomplete, has an appealing symmetrical flow.

Reference

[1] 'Symmetric group S_4 ', https://en.wikiversity.org/wiki/Symmetric_group_S4.